

A study on wettability of the dual scale by plasma etch and nanohoneycomb structure

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SUMMARY

The method is realized using a combination of a conventional plasma etch process, which creates a microscale irregularity on an aluminum surface, and an anodization process, which further modifies the plasma etched surface with nanoscale structures. The combined process enhances the wettability of the surface which gives a wide range of the contact angle from $\sim 58^\circ$ down to 0° (i.e., a complete wetting surface).

Keywords: Nanohoneycomb, Plasma etch, Superhydrophilic surface, Dual-scale, Anodization

INTRODUCTION

Due to the advent of nanotechnology, a variety of nanostructure fabrication methods are developed for different engineering applications using various hi-tech equipments, mostly depend on micromachining techniques including lithography [1], template method [2], ion bombardment [3,4], chemical deposition [5], self-assembled monolayer (SAM) [6], and photocatalyst [7,8]. However, these methods can only be applied on a flat surface with limited area (e.g., wafer level). Here, we introduce a simple, inexpensive, yet effective method to make a nano-engineered surface which can practically be used on a large area and virtually any shape of surfaces. Our method is inspired from our mother nature's hierarchical layout (i.e., the combination of micro/nanoscale modification on a surface) such as the surface of lotus leaf and the sole of gecko's foot. Many of these surfaces from nature show non-wetting property, which is the contact angle of a water droplet reaches almost 180° , due to their hydrophobically coated surface with the micro/nanostructures. However, our method is targeted for the opposite extreme of contact angle which is a complete wetting surface showing 0° contact angle without the hydrophobic coating since such wetting surface is also important for engineering purposes [9,10].

The wetting phenomena of the structured surfaces have been widely studied recently since the wettability of the solid surface is a major interest in many microfluidic applications [11]. The wettability depends on the free energy of the intrinsic material and the geometry of its surface [12,13]. Since the first parameter is the material property

which is a constant value for a given material, it is important to develop an effective method to fabricate the nano-engineered surface, which modifies the geometry of the surface.

Our fabrication method uses two fundamentals which are the concept of Wenzel's equation [24], and the capillary effect. Wenzel's equation applies to equilibrium angles on a rough surface which normally gives a lower apparent contact angle (i.e., more wetting) compared to its intrinsic contact angle on the flat surface of the same material. This roughness effect can be simply accomplished by the plasma etching process from our fabrication method. Once the rough surface is formed, then the anodization process is applied in order to make nanohole structures on the roughened surface. Since the rough surface provides more surface area than a flat surface, the density of the nanoholes per unit area is increased. Therefore the apparent contact is further reduced due to the capillary effect of the nanoholes enhancing the wettability of the surface.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

For our experiment, we prepare industrial grade aluminum (99.5 %) sheets (50 mm x 40 mm x 1 mm) and conduct the plasma etching process using ICP-Etcher (Inductively coupled plasma etcher). The plasma etching conditions are respectively 300 W, 15 mTorr, Ar 50 sccm + Cl₂ 15 sccm + BCl₃ 40 sccm and 10 min as power, pressure, mixed gas and time. We form a micro structure to plasma etching process. After plasma etching, the aluminum sheet is cleaned for next process by dipping in acetone for ten minutes and rinsed with deionized water. Then the plasma etched aluminum sheet is electrochemically etched using an oxalic acid solution. The anodization process is carried out in 0.3 M oxalic acid solution. During the anodization process, the aluminum sheet is used as an anode and a flat platinum sheet is used as a cathode. The distance between the cathode and the anode is adjusted to 5 cm. And a constant voltage of 40 VDC is applied between the cathode and the anode for 10 hours. The temperature of the solution is maintained at 15 °C by a circulator (Lab. Companion, RW-0525G) during entire anodizing process, and the constant voltage is applied by a computer-interfaced power supply (Digital electronics CO., LTD., DRP-92001DUS). After the anodization process, the aluminum sheet is rinsed with deionized water and dried for the wettability characterization. Fig. 1 shows the overall process scheme for preparing the dual-scale surface.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2(a-c) shows top views of SEM images showing the four different types of the tested samples including the normal industrial aluminum surface and the modified surfaces. Fig 2(a) is the image of the normal aluminum surface which shows a flat surface as our reference surface. Fig. 2(b) shows the plasma etched surface which contains the microscale roughness on the aluminum surface. Figure 2(c) shows the dual-scale modified surface which exhibits both the micro- and nanoscale effect.

Fig. 3 shows the optical images of the contact measurements on our samples in Fig.2. From the Fig. 3, it is clear to see that the dramatic changes in surface wettability is possible due to the surface modifications. Each contact angle measurement, which represents the surface wettability of the normal aluminum surface and each surface modification process, shows the contact angle variations from $\sim 103^\circ$ down to 0° on the same material. Fig. 3(a) shows the intrinsic contact angle of the flat aluminum surface and Fig. 3(b, c) show various contact angles due to the modifications on the reference surface. Fig. 3(b) and 3(c) indicate the intermediate contact angles which represent the controllability of the wettability on same material depending on the application needs. Fig. 2(c) shows our targeted surface (i.e., a complete wetting surface) using the dual-scale surface modification. The contribution of the microscale roughness and the capillary enhancement due to the nanoscale holes make possible to form such surface.

CONCLUSIONS

A practical complete wetting surface was fabricated by dual-scale surface modification. The first stage is plasma etching, which generates microscale unevenness on the Al surface. The resulting plasma etched Al surface was then anodized. The anodized Al oxide surface contained nanoscale hole structures. The resulting dual-scale surface was like the reverse side of the lotus leaf, having superhydrophilic property and a CA of zero. This is due to a synergetic effect between the two fabrication processes, which extremely increased the capillary force. Our complete wetting surface can be used in many heating/cooling related consumer and industrial products to act as an effective condensation surface which can efficiently and selectively collect moisture in the system to improve the performance of the products. Since aluminum is the most common material in many of these products, we can directly apply our method without any cost of additional materials. Moreover, the described fabrication method can possibly be applied in various materials as long as the materials are able to be anodized to form nanoscale holes.

Figure 1. Overall process scheme for preparing the dual-scale surface.

Figure 2. Field-emission SEM images of the tested samples.

(a) SEM image of the normal industrial aluminum surface (top view),

(b) the plasma etched aluminum surface (top view),

(c) the dual-scale modified aluminum surface (top view)

Figure 3. Optical images of the contact measurements on the sample surfaces as described in Fig. 2.

(a) Optical image on the normal aluminum showing contact angle of 103° ,

(b) on the plasma etched aluminum surface showing contact angle of 58° ,

(c) on the dual-scale modified aluminum surface showing contact angle of 0° .

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